

TARA_	YYYY	MM	DD	PORT (CITY)	LAT DD	MM.MMM	LONG DDD	MM.MMM
Start	2021	10	15	Salvador de Bahia	S 12	58.169	W 038	30.596
End	2021	11	03	Rio de Janeiro	S 22	53.376	W 043	10.432

CAMPAING OBJECTIVE

The Tara Oceans Mission Microbiome Leg 8 took place between *Salvador de Bahia* and *Rio de Janeiro*, Brazil. It corresponded to the first *AtlantECO* "Biodiscovery" leg, the first case Study on "Molecular Bioprospecting" of the mission. The two principal objectives of this leg were 1) to augment plankton biodiversity discovery through replicated omics samplings, and 2) to enable the potential discovery of new bioproducts & chemicals for industrial applications with high socio-economic value, such as new ways to produce pharmaceutical products or natural enzymes able to digest complex molecules such as pollutants or plastics. Given the bioprospecting focus of this leg, sampling stations were all located within international waters, along the Vitória-Trindade Chain (VTC) consisting of 11 heterogeneous seamounts. Due to this location, an additional objective of this leg was 3) to produce samples potentially also valuable for the H2020 EU-funded All-Atlantic sister project iAtlantic (*Integrated Assessment of Atlantic Marine Ecosystems in Space and Time*), which overall goal is to measure the impact of climate change on the Atlantic, and notably on deep-sea corals of the VTC seamounts. In line with these objectives, the main questions we wish to address are: a) Are we under-sampling the functional and taxonomic biodiversity of marine microbiomes? What are the "rare" species? (Is everything everywhere?); b) What is the nutrient/light dynamics of a DCM? Is the DCM a vertically homogeneous feature or is it made of vertically separated niches? and c) What are the pelagic microbiomes associated with deep coral reefs? Can we characterize the vertical connectivity between the pelagic microbiomes and deep-sea corals (e.g., downward export of organic matter, using a genomic signature)? What is the survival of coral larvae in the pelagic ecosystem?

PARTICIPANTS

	ROLE	NAME, Surname, Affiliation
1	CREW - Captain	AUDRAIN Samuel (SA)
2	CREW - 1st Officer	TOURNON Yves (YT)
3	CREW - Mecano	BOULON Léo (LB)
4	CREW - Deck	MONMARCHÉ David (DM)
5	CREW - Deck	PRIEUR Alain (AP)
6	CREW - Cook	BIN Sophie
7	CREW - Media	LARIE Arthur
8	GUEST - Artist	LANJOUÈRE Manon
9	GUEST - Observer	DE OLIVEIRA PAULA Anderson (Capitão-tenente)
10	SCIENCE - A - Oceano. Engineer	LINKOWSKI Thomas (TL)
11	SCIENCE - B - Chief Scientist	CHAFFRON Samuel (SC)
12	SCIENCE - C - W-Lab genomics	COUET Douglas (DC)
13	SCIENCE - D - S-Lab biogeochemistry	BECKER Érica (EB)

14	SCIENCE - E - S-Lab sorting/imaging	JUNGER Pedro (PJ)
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ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The area sampled is located at the border of the Brazilian South Atlantic gyre, one of the most oligotrophic subtropical zones of the global ocean, which is characterized by a strong oligotrophic status and minimal chlorophyll concentration as compared to the whole ocean (1). The zone was previously sampled in 2010, at [Station 076](#) during the Tara Oceans expedition (2009-2013). Sampling stations of Leg 8 were located eastward and around the Vitória-Trindade Chain (VTC) that extend 1,150 km off the eastern coast of Brazil to Trindade Island and the Martim Vaz Archipelago in the Atlantic Ocean (2). The VTC consists of 11 heterogeneous seamounts that can reach euphotic and mesophotic zones (10–110 m depth), and includes in particular the Jaseur seamounts (<https://www.marinerregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=6697>), the Davis Bank (<https://www.marinerregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=6679>), and the Dogaressa seamounts (<https://www.marinerregions.org/gazetteer.php?p=details&id=6681>). During this leg, the latter two seamounts were targeted and sampled during 12 working days at 10 sampling stations represented in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Sampling stations (46 to 55) of MM Leg 8 (KML file available).

The following 10 stations were sampled during Leg 8 around Dogaressa and Davis seamounts:

- **Station 46:** The purpose of this first station, on the way to Dogaressa seamounts, was mainly to train on our protocols and to test our organization as operators on board, in order to be prepared for more intense sampling stations around and above the seamounts. We observed a clear and well stratified DCM at 140m, with Chlorophyll detected up to 220m (**Figure 2**), features that we actually consistently observed at all stations during the leg! At this station, we sampled duplicates at the surface for all protocols. This will be useful to address objective 1) by testing the effect of replicates on the biodiversity discovery.

Figure 2: CTD profile observed at Station 46.

- **Station 47:** At this long station, located Eastward of the Dogaressa seamounts, we performed 2 day-samplings and 1 night-sampling in the epipelagic zone to finely characterize the DCM in order to address objective 2). As in the previous station (#46), we also observed a deep DCM at 140m with Chlorophyll detected up to 220m as well. The 2 days and 1 full-night samplings should allow us to acquire useful data to finely characterize a deep DCM with Chla as deep as 225m. Here, we sampled the Chla profile at 6 depths (70m, 110m, DCM=130m, 150m, 175m, 200m) and at the surface.
- **Stations 48 to 50:** These stations were dedicated to sample the epipelagic zone within the seamounts, in order to evaluate the seamount effect on plankton diversity. At these 3 stations we performed fast casts to study the connectivity between both long stations (47 and 51). These short stations samplings (deep casts at 1000m) should allow us to study the connectivity between water column & deep reef systems, with stations between Dogaressa and Davis seamounts, and then stations westward of Davis. These samplings will also likely be useful to study the potential mass seamounts effect on plankton diversity and productivity.
- **Station 51:** At this second long station, located Westward of the Dogaressa seamounts, we performed the same samplings as in station 47, that is 2 day-samplings in the epipelagic zone to finely characterize the DCM in order to address objective 2). Here, we also observed a deep DCM at 130m with Chlorophyll detected up to 200m, and we sampled the Chla profile at 6 depths (70m, 110m, DCM=130m, 150m, 175m, 200m) and at the surface, but did not perform the full-night samplings.
- **Station 52 to 55:** These stations were also dedicated to sample the epipelagic zone within the seamounts, in order to evaluate the seamount effect on plankton diversity. At these 4

stations we performed 3 fast casts and 1 surface samplings (including eDNA samplings) to study the connectivity between stations, but also to address objective 3) to produce samples also valuable to our All-Atlantic sister project *iAtlantic* (Figure 3), with the goal to assess connectivity across VTC seamounts and in particular regarding the colonization of deep-sea corals in the area through larvae dissemination.

Figure 3: Sampling stations planned by the *iAtlantic* project around Davis and Dogaressa seamounts.

MAJOR ACHIEVEMENTS & SCIENTIFIC INTERESTS

Overall, this leg 8 went very well and the whole team was very happy and satisfied by the work accomplished. The collected samples will allow to address both main objectives of this leg. First, replicated samples done in surface will be particularly useful to augment the biodiversity discovery at these South Atlantic oligotrophic stations (Stations 46, 51, and 55). Second, the fine-scale characterization of the observed deep DCM (at 130-140m) in stratified waters at both long stations 47 and 51, which included 7 depths (0, 70, 110, 130, 150, 170, and 200m), as well as overnight samplings at station 47, will allow us to study the nutrient/light dynamics of a DCM as well as the vertical biodiversity and ecology of a DCM.

Anecdotally, after sampling station 52 above Davis seamount, we had the opportunity to swim in the afternoon, while chasing seamounts reaching about 20m under sea level. After some time, four of us actually observed the top of one seamount “needle” reaching about 28m below surface, surrounded by fishes at the bottom and at the surface, incredible! 😊

REFERENCES

1. A. Morel, H. Claustre, B. Gentili, The most oligotrophic subtropical zones of the global ocean: similarities and differences in terms of chlorophyll and yellow substance. *Biogeosciences* **7**, 3139-3151 (2010). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/bg-7-3139-2010>
2. P. M. Meirelles *et al.*, Baseline Assessment of Mesophotic Reefs of the Vitoria-Trindade Seamount Chain Based on Water Quality, Microbial Diversity, Benthic Cover and Fish Biomass Data. *PLoS One* **10**, e0130084 (2015). <http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0130084>

INVENTORY OF SAMPLES COLLECTED DURING THE CAMPAIGN

		Storage T°C			Box size			Chemical					
		10	10	10	4	4	4	-20	-20	-20	-80	-80	-80
											#1	#2	#3
Protocol	Container type												
DGAS	ExeV-12mL												
Dec-13	200-mL-Bottle	15											
DICTA	500-mL-bottle	15											
DO18	AmberV-40mL	15											
NUT-1	20mLCryoV				20								
SAL	125-mL Bottle	15											
DINO	60-mL-Bottle				15								
HG-M	125-mL Bottle	14											
MB320	4-mL-Vial							20					
MB023	4-mL-Vial							20					
MB<02	50-mL-falcon										20		
eDNA	sterivex										25		
NP550	20-mL-vial										17		
NP045	4-mL-Vial							17					
HG	Zip-lock	15											
PM	Zip-lock	22											
S320	5-mL-cryotube										32		
S023	5-mL-cryotube										27		
S<02	5-mL-cryotube							21					
P320	5-mL-cryotube										19		
P023	5-mL-cryotube										19		
HP	2-mL-cryotube										43		
SG	5-mL-cryotube										51		

FC	2-mL-cryotube				78
HC	2-mL-cryotube				64
SEM	petri-slide	17			
FM20	50-mL-falcon		20		
E20	15-mL-falcon			10	
S20	5-mL-cryotube				10
S20-L	5-mL-falcon			10	
PM-HG20	Zip-lock	10			
MB20	4-mL-Vial			10	
CP50	petri-slide	10			
SCP50	petri-slide	5			
F200	250-mL-bottle				10
E200	15-mL-falcon			10	
S200	5-mL-cryotube				10
S200-L	5-mL-falcon			10	
PM-HG200	Zip-lock	10			
MB200	4-mL-Vial			10	
CP200	petri-slide	10			
F680	250-mL-bottle				3
F2000	250-mL-bottle				4
E680	15-mL-falcon			3	
S680-L	MULTIPLATES				3
E2000	15-mL-falcon			5	
AI	petri-slide	42			
AS	2-mL-cryotube				42
AF	Zip-lock			42	
SP300	2-mL-cryotube				27

